

The Role of Content Marketing and Social Media Marketing in Creating Customer Engagement in a Beauty Clinic

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ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
01 October 2025

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the role of *Content* and Social Media Marketing in increasing *Customer Engagement* at Beauty Clinics in South Kalimantan. This study was conducted at 48 beauty clinics spread across South Kalimantan Province. The research population consists of customers who have visited beauty clinics more than once. This study uses descriptive analysis, which requires sufficient analysis units ranging from 100 to 200. Considering the loyal behavior toward beauty clinic services, the research population was four times that of beauty clinics (48 beauty clinics) spread across three major cities in South Kalimantan. Therefore, the research population consists of: $4 \times 48 = 192$ customers who consume beauty clinic services. The sampling technique used in this study is the census method. The results show that *customer engagement* can be a social media strategy for beauty clinics in driving *content marketing* and utilizing *social media marketing* to maintain *customer engagement*, making it an appropriate strategy for *social media marketing* to retain customers and *content marketing*.

KEYWORDS: Content Marketing; social media marketing; customer engagement.

INTRODUCTION

As times change and information media evolve, marketing strategies employed by several companies are also affected. The use of social media is now commonplace in marketing and promotion. However, its functions extend beyond that, with many other benefits available through social media. Social media is an *online* medium where users can easily participate, share, and create content, including *blogs*, social networks, wikis, forums, and virtual worlds. *Blogs*, social networks, and wikis are the most commonly used forms of social media by people worldwide. Another opinion states that social media is an *online* medium that supports social interaction and uses web-based technology to transform communication into interactive dialogue. Social media also has a set of new communication and collaboration tools that enable various types of interaction previously unavailable to the general public (Brogan, 2010).

This creates opportunities for businesses to use the internet extensively as a marketing medium, which is therefore known as *digital marketing*. *Digital marketing* is an activity, institution, and process facilitated by digital technology in realizing, communicating, and conveying values to consumers and other interested parties (Kannan &

Hongshuang, 2016). Increasingly, the development of internet technology has rendered conventional marketing techniques ineffective, as human mobility is shifting towards digital trends. This is evident in the number of businesses that carry out promotions through *digital marketing*. However, *digital marketing* is used by companies to promote their products or services and to compete in distributing content created by the company. Companies must convey something unique, engaging, and educational to their consumers. If companies continue only to display direct promotions on their product details, this method is considered less attractive and boring to consumers. Therefore, the term content marketing has emerged.

As a clinic with a customer segment consisting of millennials, a group of young people born between the early 1980s and early 2000s, and Gen Z, born after the 2000s, both of whom are highly active on social media, the Beauty Clinic in South Kalimantan has made a breakthrough by promoting and marketing itself through social media. To increase the interest and engagement of potential customers, the clinic adds educational and engaging content. This marketing-oriented content will enhance *customer engagement* at Idaman Hati Inpatient Clinic. Based on the

background description, the objectives to be achieved are: To describe *content marketing*, *social media marketing*, and *customer engagement* at beauty clinics in South Kalimantan. There are three benefits of this research, which are as follows.

The benefits of this research are expected to contribute to understanding customer behavior theory and emotional relationships with companies as brand owners in the context of loyalty, marketing strategies, including content marketing measurements, and marketing activities using social media strategies. For beauty clinic managers in South Kalimantan, this research can contribute to managers, in this case, company leaders/clinic managers who are oriented towards improving marketing performance to retain customers and maintain sustainable sales turnover in the current era of digitalization and advances in communication technology. Discussions about the influence of *content* and *social media marketing* on customer loyalty, mediated by *customer engagement*, are important for company leaders/clinic managers to improve their business performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Customer Engagement: Definition of *Customer Engagement*. *Customer engagement* is a psychological state highly dependent on context, characterized by a certain level of intensity that plays an important role in the relational exchange process (Brodie, 2011). *Customer engagement* is above customer loyalty, where an emotional relationship between the company and the customer is established. *Customer engagement* has emerged due to developments in technology and information, particularly the internet. The interactive nature of the internet supports two-way communication between *customers* and companies. This enables companies to convey information and messages to consumers, and *customers* can also provide *feedback* to companies.

Aspects of Customer Engagement: *Customer engagement* has three aspects (Brodie, 2011). Cognitive Aspect, This dimension relates to the effects that arise in a person that are informative in nature concerning knowledge and expectations. Emotional Aspect: This dimension refers to a person's feelings and attitudes about their mood. Behavioral Aspect concerns an individual's presence and how they interact with others. **Customer Engagement Indicators:** *Customer engagement* is customers' *physical*, *cognitive*, and *emotional* involvement in establishing a relationship with a company (Gummerus *et al.*, 2012). There are three indicators of *customer engagement* (Yuningsih, 2018): Attractiveness, Products can be packaged with attractive promotions to make them more appealing to the audience. Creating appeal for the audience is at the heart of promotion. A product's attractive features should be highlighted in the promotion. Goals to be achieved: The goals that an organization or company wants to achieve within a specific

period. Missions or goals often form the basis for decision-making within the organization, so companies need to have clear and focused missions. The message conveyed is a process whereby individuals, groups, organizations, and communities create and use information to connect with their environment and others. Communication can be verbal or nonverbal. Verbal communication is conducted through spoken words, while nonverbal communication involves body language or gestures, such as smiling, shaking the head, and shrugging the shoulders.

Social Media Marketing, Definition of *social media marketing*: *Social media marketing* is a form of marketing that utilizes social media to create, communicate, convey information, and promote to influence consumers, build loyalty, and increase interaction (Wimsatt, 2018). *Social media marketing* is a medium for monitoring and facilitating consumers to interact and positively engage with companies and their brands (Dave Chaffey, 2016). *Social media marketing* is also considered the use of social media sites to carry out general marketing activities that can display engaging content to attract the audience's attention and trigger them to spread the content, which will help the company expand its reach (Alhadeed, 2017).

Content Marketing: Definition of *Content Marketing*. *Content marketing* involves creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract the target audience's attention. Content can convey information or messages to the people who see it. With the increasing ease of access to the internet and media, *content marketing* is one of the most powerful marketing strategies. The development of world marketing is increasingly expanding, especially with the emergence of various ways to implement various marketing strategies. Currently, marketing communication is not only done through conventional means, but also through other media, namely *content marketing*.

Content marketing involves creating, curating, distributing, and strengthening content to make it interesting, relevant, and useful for specific groups to create discussions about the content (Kotler *et al.*, 2017). *Content marketing* aims to offer print and digital media content relevant to the target market. Consequently, content must be specifically designed to meet the target market's needs. This situation then gives rise to the phenomenon of "*media rent to media own*" (Pandrianto & Sukendro, 2018). In this context, *content marketing* refers to activities prioritizing content in branding or product marketing.

METHOD

3.1 Research Design

The research design used in this study is descriptive research, which describes each variable studied, explains its strengths, and compares its magnitude using analysis.

3.2 Research Scope

The scope of this research covers variables related to the field of marketing. This research examines the variables of *content marketing* and *social media marketing* in the context of their relationship with *customer engagement*.

3.3 Research Location

This study was conducted in forty-eight (48) favorite beauty clinics or those chosen by consumers for beauty services in South Kalimantan (source: South Kalimantan Provincial Health Office, 2023). First, the researchers selected three large cities: Banjarmasin, Banjarbaru, and Kotabaru. After that, they determined the names of the beauty clinics.

3.4 Research Instruments

A questionnaire or survey is a set of written questions or statements about factual data or opinions related to the respondent, which are known facts or truths that need to be answered by the respondent (Sugiyono, 2019). The data collection techniques used in this study were questionnaires and observation. The preparation of questionnaires needs to pay attention to several things, namely, there must be an introduction or instructions for filling them out, the questions must be formulated clearly using commonly used words, the sentences must not be too long, and the questions or statements must be structured according to the respondents' answer columns. The questionnaire was distributed using a *Likert* scale, namely using a score of 1-5.

3.5 Data Analysis Techniques

Descriptive analysis is intended to explain each description or characteristic of the variables studied, namely *Content marketing* (X1), *Social media marketing* (X2), and *Customer Engagement* (Y₁). The analysis technique used is *descriptive statistics*, namely frequency distribution analysis (mode) and central tendency measures (*mean*), used to describe each variable, indicator, and statement item.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

The research respondents were customers of a well-known beauty clinic in South Kalimantan. The respondent profile based on gender is presented in the Table.

Table 1. Gender of Research Respondents

Gender	Number	Percentage
Male	41	21.4
Female	151	78.6
Total	192	100

Source: processed primary data, 2025

Table 1 presents the gender of beauty clinic customers in the South Kalimantan research location. The results show that most of them are female, at 78.6%. This comparison indicates that women still dominate beauty treatments

compared to men. Next, the respondents' profiles based on occupation are presented in a table.

Table 2. Respondent Job Type Profile

Type of Work	Number	Percentage
1. Civil Servant / ASN	64	33
2. Entrepreneurs	32	16.7
3. Private institutions	96	50
Total	192	100

Source: processed primary data, 2025

Table 2 explains the types of jobs of the respondents studied. The category of civil servants (PNS) or state civil servants (ASN) was 33.3% more than entrepreneurs at 16.7%. Most of the research respondents worked in private institutions (50%). This finding shows that most beauty salon customers in South Kalimantan are employees with a fixed income (salary) from the state or the institutions where they work.

Descriptive analysis results. This study used a questionnaire as a data collection tool. There were two exogenous variables, namely *Content Marketing* and *Media Marketing*. There was one endogenous variable, *Customer Loyalty*, and one mediating variable, *Customer Engagement*. The total number of questionnaire items was 30. Respondents' answers were measured using a Likert scale. The results of the responses from 192 respondents are shown by the *mean* value of respondents' perceptions and *the mode* value of the Likert scale options. The beauty clinic visited was in line with the needs of 87 respondents (45.3%). This was followed by 77 respondents (40.1%) who strongly agreed. Twenty-seven respondents (14.1%) were neutral. One respondent (0.5%) disagreed, and zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.25. Most respondents agreed that the beauty clinic they visited met their needs.

The distribution of respondents' answers regarding *Content Marketing*, discussing whether the facilities of the beauty clinic visited met their expectations, showed that 66 respondents (34.4%) strongly agreed, followed by 70 respondents (36.5%) who agreed. Twenty respondents (10.4%) stated they were neutral. Thirty-five respondents (18.2%) stated they disagreed, and one respondent (0.5%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.24. This indicates that most respondents agree that the facilities at the beauty clinic they visited met their expectations. The distribution of respondents' answers regarding *Content Marketing*, which states that the beauty clinic visited does not have boring advertisements, shows that 97 respondents (50.5%) strongly agree, followed by 69 respondents (35.9%)

who agree. Seventeen respondents (8.9%) are neutral. Nine respondents (4.7%) disagreed, and zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.32. This indicates that the majority of respondents strongly agree that the beauty clinic they visited has advertisements that are not boring.

The distribution of respondents' answers regarding Content Marketing, which discusses that the intensity of visits to beauty clinics is not dull, shows that 85 respondents (44.3%) strongly agree, followed by 67 respondents (34.9%) who agree. Thirty-three respondents (17.2%) are neutral. Seven respondents (3.6%) strongly disagreed, and zero (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.19. This indicates that most respondents strongly agreed that the intensity of visits to beauty clinics was not dull. The distribution of respondents' answers regarding Content Marketing, discussing that the beauty clinic advertisements visited can be easily understood, shows that 97 respondents (50.5%) strongly agree, followed by 75 respondents (39.1%) who agree. Nineteen respondents (9.9%) are neutral. One respondent (0.5%) strongly disagreed, and zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.39. This indicates that most respondents strongly agree that the advertisements for the beauty clinics they visited were easy to understand.

The distribution of respondents' answers regarding Content Marketing, which discusses, shows that the public can easily understand the marketing communication of the beauty clinic visited. Sixty-three respondents (32.8%) strongly agree, followed by 69 respondents (35.9%) who agree. Fifty-nine respondents (30.7%) are neutral. One respondent (0.5%) disagreed, and zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.01. This indicates that most respondents agree that the public can easily understand the marketing communication of the visited beauty clinic. The distribution of respondents' answers regarding *content marketing*, which discusses that the beauty clinic visited provides information about the products offered, shows that 111 respondents (57.8%) strongly agree, followed by 73 respondents (38.0%) who agree. Six respondents (3.1%) are neutral. Two respondents (1.0%) disagreed, and zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.52. This indicates that most respondents strongly agree that the beauty clinic they visited provides information about the products offered. The distribution of respondents' answers regarding *content marketing*, which discusses that the beauty clinic visited is easy to find, shows that 95 respondents (49.5%) strongly agree, followed by 87 respondents (45.3%) who agree. Eight respondents (4.2%) are neutral. Two respondents (1.0%) disagreed, and zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.43. This indicates that most respondents strongly agree that the beauty clinic they visited is easy to find.

The distribution of respondents' answers regarding *content marketing*, which discusses that the beauty clinic visited has information that can be trusted to be true, shows that 71 respondents (37.0%) strongly agree, followed by 68 respondents (35.4%) who agree. Forty-two respondents (21.9%) are neutral. Eleven respondents (5.7%) disagreed, and zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.03. This indicates that most respondents strongly agree that the beauty clinic they visited has reliable and truthful information. The distribution of respondents' answers regarding *content marketing*, which discusses that the beauty clinic visited consistently provides services to consumers, shows that 92 respondents (47.9%) strongly agree, followed by 72 respondents (37.5%) who agree. Twenty-seven respondents (14.1%) are neutral. One respondent (0.5%) strongly disagreed, and zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.32. This indicates that most respondents strongly agree that the beauty clinic they visited consistently provides services to consumers.

Social Media Marketing in beauty clinics visited has an attractive appearance, with the highest number of respondents agreeing strongly, totaling 109 respondents (56.8%). This was followed by 74 respondents (38.5%) who strongly agreed. Six respondents (3.1%) were neutral. Three respondents (1.6%) strongly disagreed, and zero (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.51, indicating that most respondents agreed that beauty clinics should appear attractive. The distribution of respondents' answers regarding the credibility of the context advertised by beauty clinics shows that 100 respondents (52.17%) strongly agree. This is followed by 83 respondents (43.2%) who agree. Seven respondents (3.6%) are neutral. Two respondents (1.0%) disagreed, and zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score was 4.50, indicating that most respondents strongly agreed that the context advertised by beauty clinics is credible based on the credibility possessed by the clinics. Respondents' answers regarding communication between consumers and employees at the beauty clinics they visited were good, with 100 respondents (52.1%) stating that they strongly agreed. This was followed by 83 respondents (43.2%) who agreed, seven respondents (3.6%) who were neutral, two respondents (1.0%) who disagreed, and zero respondents (0.0%) who strongly disagreed. The average score obtained was 4.51. This indicates that most strongly agreed that communication between customers and employees at the beauty clinic they visited was well established. Respondents' answers regarding communication between consumers and employees at the beauty clinics they visited provided insight for consumers, with 88 respondents (45.8%) stating that they strongly agreed. This was followed by 78 respondents (40.6%) who agreed. Fifteen respondents (7.8%) were neutral. Seven respondents (3.6%) disagreed, and four

(2.1%) strongly disagreed. The average score obtained was 4.25. This indicates that the majority strongly agree that communication between consumers and employees at the beauty clinic visited can provide understanding for consumers. Respondents' answers regarding collaboration involving beauty clinics visited by consumers showed that employees could collaborate with consumers to align perceptions about consumer desires. The results showed that 95 respondents (49.5%) strongly agreed. This was followed by 73 respondents (38.0%) who agreed. 11 respondents (5.7%) were neutral. Seven respondents (3.6%) disagreed. Moreover, six respondents (3.1%) strongly disagreed. The average score obtained was 4.31. This shows that the majority strongly agree that collaboration, discussing the beauty clinics visited by consumers, enables employees to collaborate with consumers to align perceptions about consumer desires.

Respondents' answers regarding collaboration, discussing employees at beauty clinics visited, showed that 86 respondents (44.8%) strongly agreed. This was followed by 68 respondents (35.4%) who agreed. Eight respondents (4.2%) were neutral. Twenty-one respondents (10.9%) disagreed. Nine respondents (4.7%) strongly disagreed. The average score obtained was 4.05. This indicates that most strongly agree that collaboration involving employees at the beauty clinic can share knowledge with consumers. Respondents' answers regarding connection, which discusses beauty clinic employees who support each other in serving customers, showed that 79 respondents (41.1%) strongly agreed. This was followed by 71 respondents (37.0%) who agreed. Eighteen respondents (9.4%) were neutral. Twenty-four respondents (12.5%) disagreed. Moreover, zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score obtained was 4.07. This shows that the majority strongly agree that connections discussing beauty clinic employees who visit each other support their colleagues in serving customers. The respondents' answers regarding the connection that discussed beauty clinic employees who visited each other to help when colleagues experienced difficulties at work showed that 86 respondents (44.8%) strongly agreed. This was followed by 74 respondents (38.5%) who agreed. Eight respondents (4.2%) were neutral. Seventeen respondents (8.9%) disagreed. Moreover, seven respondents (3.6%) strongly disagreed. The average score obtained was 4.12. This indicates that the majority strongly agree that connections discussing how employees at the visited beauty clinic can help each other when colleagues experience difficulties at work.

Customer Engagement. Respondents' answers regarding the *attractiveness* of feeling interested in the atmosphere at the beauty clinic visited showed that 115 respondents (59.9%) strongly agreed. This was followed by 68 respondents (35.4%) who agreed. Eight respondents (4.2%) were neutral.

One respondent (0.5%) disagreed. Moreover, zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score obtained was 4.54. This indicates that the majority strongly agreed with the appeal of being interested in the atmosphere at the beauty clinic. The responses regarding the attractiveness of the beauty clinics visited, currently being able to provide professional services, resulted in 100 respondents (52.1%) strongly agreeing. This was followed by 84 respondents (43.8%) who agreed. Eight respondents (4.2%) were neutral. 0 respondents (0%) disagreed. Moreover, zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score obtained was 4.47. This shows that the majority strongly agree that the beauty clinic they currently visit can provide professional services.

The respondents' answers regarding the goal of feeling satisfied with the services at the beauty clinic they visited, because it was in line with their expectations, showed that 73 respondents (38.0%) strongly agreed. This was followed by 55 respondents (28.6%) who agreed. Thirty-two respondents (16.7%) were neutral. Twenty-three respondents (12.0%) disagreed. Moreover, nine respondents (4.7%) strongly disagreed. The average score obtained was 3.83. This indicates that the majority strongly agreed, intending to feel satisfied with the services at the beauty clinic they visited because they met their expectations.

Respondents' responses regarding the desired outcome, which discussed whether the results obtained after visiting the beauty clinic aligned with their goals, showed that 92 respondents (47.9%) strongly agreed. This was followed by 75 respondents (39.1%) who strongly agreed. Seven respondents (3.67%) were neutral. Eight respondents (4.2%) disagreed, and 10 (5.2%) strongly disagreed. The average score obtained was 4.20. This indicates that the majority strongly agreed with the respondents' desired goals, which discuss the desired outcomes obtained after visiting this beauty clinic, per the objectives.

The respondents' answers to the message, which discussed "I feel that the message conveyed by this clinic to consumers is interesting to listen to," showed that 104 respondents (54.2%) strongly agreed. This was followed by 80 respondents (41.7%) who agreed. Seven respondents (3.6%) were neutral. One respondent (0.5%) disagreed. Moreover, zero respondents (0%) strongly disagreed. The average score obtained was 4.49. This shows that the majority strongly agreed with the message conveyed by the clinic to consumers, which they found interesting to listen to. The responses to the message conveyed discussing " " (According to me, this clinic can provide accurate information according to consumer needs) showed that 99 respondents (51.6%) strongly agreed. This was followed by 81 respondents (42.2%) who strongly agreed. 11 respondents (5.7%) were neutral. One respondent (0.5%) disagreed. Moreover, zero respondents (0%) strongly

disagreed. The average score obtained was 4.44. This indicates that the majority strongly agreed that the message conveyed is that this clinic can provide accurate information according to consumer needs.

4.2 Discussion

The discussion is directed at answering the main research problem: the influence of *content* and *social media marketing* on customer loyalty mediated by *customer engagement* at beauty clinics in South Kalimantan. The discussion of the research results is described as follows: *Content Marketing*, Marketing activities by companies utilizing electronic media by distributing content in the form of interesting and valuable messages to reach specific targets (Pulizzi, 2013), is a strategy employed by many beauty clinics in South Kalimantan to gain loyal customers. According to Chairina (2020), marketing content delivered through digital media to the target market must be relevant to the business unit, namely beauty clinics. The content must be delivered accurately, be easy to understand and find on digital media, and have a stable level of consistency in digital marketing activities. Charisma's (2020) opinion, relevance, accuracy, ease of understanding, discovery, and consistency are established as research indicators. The study results show that easily found indicators explain the implementation of content marketing by beauty clinic companies in South Kalimantan. The second indicator is the relevance of content marketing to beauty services. These two indicators are important to beauty companies' digital media marketing activities. The ease of obtaining beauty service product content and the ease of information about beauty service products were findings in this study.

Social media marketing, Marketing activities to create demand for products, especially beauty services, using digital media, have become a mainstay of marketing in the service sector. Marketers consider marketing through *social media* to be capable of creating awareness, recognition, memory, and even positive action towards a particular brand or product (Santoso, 2017). The strategies implemented by beauty clinics in South Kalimantan generally involve creating and distributing engaging content, including beauty tutorials, customer testimonials, and even special promotions to retain customers or attract new consumers.

The theory proposed by Heuer (2009) explains that social media marketing indicators can be monitored through four aspects: the design of the social media model/context, the form of communication, the collaboration patterns built in marketing, and the network/connection patterns created. These four aspects are reinforced in the book *Engage* by Solis (2015). The study results indicate that context indicators can explain the implementation of marketing activities carried out by beauty clinics through social media in South Kalimantan. Strengths such as stringing words together using spelling and message content are attractive to

respondents/customers. This also means that the context/message conveyed by beauty clinics to customers is considered attractive and trustworthy.

According to Brode (2011), customer engagement is a relationship between beauty clinics and their customers, including emotional connections. Due to developments in communication technology, many service sector businesses, such as beauty clinics, rely on *customer engagement* to retain customers and prevent them from switching to other providers. The emotional communication bond between beauty clinics and customers, as described by Yuningsih (2018), can be explained through the attractiveness of beauty services, the desired goals of customers, and the messages conveyed by beauty clinic management. The study results show that the attractiveness of the beauty services offered more explains the emotional relationship between beauty clinic companies and customers. According to the respondents' perceptions, the appeal of advertisements and the professional service they have experienced form a strong emotional bond between beauty clinic companies and their customers.

CONCLUSION

This study analyzes *Content Marketing*, *Customer Engagement*, and *Social Media Marketing* at Beauty Clinics in South Kalimantan. The study's overall results can be summarized as follows: *Content marketing* is explained in terms of content easily found by beauty clinic customers in South Kalimantan. *Social media marketing* can be better explained by the context that can effectively convey information about beauty products and services. *Customer engagement*, or the emotional relationship between beauty clinic companies and customers, is better explained by the attractiveness of beauty products and services.

This research aims to develop knowledge in marketing, particularly digital marketing, which is growing rapidly. In addition to the development of knowledge in the field of marketing, this research is also intended for practitioners, in this case, entrepreneurs in the beauty clinic business in South Kalimantan. Policy makers, in terms of regulations for business competition and business licenses, also need to pay attention to the results of this research. The full contribution of the results of this study is described as follows: for owners, management, or administrators of beauty clinics in South Kalimantan. The results of this study prove that social media marketing has a dominant impact on increasing customer loyalty. This needs to be a significant concern for beauty clinic entrepreneurs in order to have customers who are loyal to the company. This means that good communication with customers must be established by creating attractive promotional content through various social media *platforms* owned by each beauty clinic. In addition, entrepreneurs and employees can also collaborate

with social media *influencers* by building connections with various parties interested in the beauty clinic business.

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